

Appendix

Table I: Collectives, participants, land use and landscape types per Province (*own information, **CBS Statistics Netherlands 2019, ***CLO Environmental Data Compendium Netherlands 2013).

Province	Number of collectives *	Participants in the AES in 2020*	Land area (km ²)**	Population density (inhabitants/km ²)**	Permanent grassland (% of cultivated land) **	Arable farming (% of cultivated land) **	Landscape types***
Groningen	3	700	2,324	251	30.1	52.9	coastal zone, peat area, peat colony, sea clay area
Friesland	7	1875	3,336	194	68.5	9.6	coastal zone, peat area, sea clay area
Drenthe	1	362	2,633	187	28.3	40.4	peat colony, sandy area
Overijssel	3	876	3,319	348	54.8	8.8	peat area, river area, sandy area
Flevoland	1	101	1,412	295	4.5	69.0	drained area
Gelderland	3	2072	4,964	417	52.1	10.6	river area, sandy area
Utrecht	4	896	1,485	904	72.3	1.7	peat area, river area, sandy area
Noord-Holland	4	814	2,665	1.071	34.4	23.5	coastal zone, drained area, peat area, sea clay area
Zuid-Holland	8	1160	2,700	1.361	44.8	30.0	coastal zone, peat area, sea clay area
Zeeland	1	323	1,782	215	7.4	69.8	coastal zone, sea clay area
Noord-Brabant	4	888	4,905	519	18.8	31.1	river area, sea clay area, sandy area
Limburg	1	1313	2,147	520	16.7	39.3	hilly area, river area, sandy area

References:

CBS Statistics Netherlands (2019). Regionale Kerncijfers.

<https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/#/CBS/nl/dataset/70072ned/table?dl=440F3> [accessed on 28/10/20].

CLO Environmental Data Compendium Netherlands (2013). Landschapstypologie.

<https://www.clo.nl/indicatoren/nl1005-landschapstypologie> [accessed on 28/10/20].

Table II: Statements of the questionnaire for assessing the importance of different motivations.

Motivational category	Statement in English	Statement in Dutch	Explanation
	Farmers participate...	Deelnemers doen mee...	
A1) Direct monetary rewards	...because they are rewarded with money.	...omdat ze beloond worden met geld.	
A2) Indirect rewards	...due to advantages for their farm business (e.g. natural pest control) or marketing (like earning sustainability labels for products).	...vanwege voordelen voor het bedrijf (bijvoorbeeld natuurlijke plaagbestrijding) of marketing (zoals het verdienen van duurzaamheidskeurmerken voor producten).	<i>We decided to provide examples here for a better understanding. The examples are tailored to the Dutch context.</i>
A3) Cost savings	...due to cost savings resulting from the collective approach.	...vanwege kostenbesparingen door collectieve aanpak.	
B1) Problem awareness	...because they find nature important.	...omdat ze de natuur belangrijk vinden.	<i>We assumed that farmers who participate because they find nature important are at least aware of single problem aspects like the decline of birds. There may be a wide range of problem awareness, from those who care about single aspects to those who think rather of agro-ecological-systems.</i>
B2) Perceived responsibility	...because they feel responsible for nature conservation.	...omdat ze zich verantwoordelijk voelen voor natuurbeheer.	
B3) Group efficacy	...because working on nature conservation as a group increases effects for nature.	...omdat het werken aan natuurbeheer in een groep grotere milieueffecten heeft.	<i>We assumed that a farmer who acknowledges higher conservation effects by the collective approach believes in the effort of each group member to reach common targets. There is trust instead of concern about free-riding and the awareness that coordinated measures result in higher effects for the region.</i>
C1) Injunctive norms	...due to a strong tradition of collective nature conservation.	...vanwege een sterke traditie van collectief natuurbeheer.	<i>We decided to operationalize this category according to the Dutch context where many farmer collectives partially have experience in working together for more than ten years before the new scheme started. We assumed that there may be farmers who are already long-term participants who internalized group norms like commitment to conservation.</i>
C2) Descriptive norms	...due to involvement of colleagues.	...vanwege betrokkenheid van collega's.	<i>We operationalized this category with peer pressure, that a farmer participates to follow the example of colleagues by whom the farmer wants to be respected.</i>

Table III and IV: Further results from the Principle Component Analysis in R.

III) Eigenvalues and proportion of variances:

	eigenvalue	variance.percent	cumulative.variance.percent
Dim.1	3.0280818	37.851023	37.85102
Dim.2	1.3793002	17.241252	55.09227
Dim.3	1.0137542	12.671927	67.76420
Dim.4	0.8068134	10.085168	77.84937
Dim.5	0.6817547	8.521934	86.37130
Dim.6	0.4698930	5.873662	92.24497
Dim.7	0.4167190	5.208988	97.45395
Dim.8	0.2036837	2.546047	100.00000

IV) Contributions of the variables:

	Dim.1	Dim.2	Dim.3	Dim.4	Dim.5	Dim.6	Dim.7	Dim.8
A1)	6.877406	16.6602150	4.9472224	22.1861412	48.1041727	0.6809806	0.2528333	0.291029195
A2)	1.050393	36.7515165	2.2940100	46.2600776	0.7040955	11.4144433	1.5248045	0.000659142
A3)	2.644031	31.0758893	17.4146655	18.5581318	15.0382008	6.9385490	6.0741435	2.256389655
B1)	23.302472	3.7642082	1.1921085	0.8204040	12.3596887	0.5284264	8.8291635	49.203528952
B2)	22.298614	0.5386677	10.0453459	0.1869147	13.1588091	0.0846208	6.8282304	46.858797189
B3)	20.314747	1.6563830	0.1569287	3.7935453	1.9498994	30.3596084	41.6743211	0.094566881
C1)	15.342184	7.2546083	9.3301969	7.3845071	1.6976246	44.9128207	14.0391249	0.038933292
C2)	8.170153	2.2985119	54.6195222	0.8102783	6.9875093	5.0805508	20.7773788	1.256095694